

Thermodynamics of Cation Exchange in Tantalum Arsenate

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The equilibrium exchange of Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , La^{3+} and Th^{4+} ions with the hydrogen form of tantalum arsenate at a constant ionic strength of 0.1N in the reaction :

has been studied. Solid phase activity coefficients for the exchanging ions and free energy changes have been evaluated from the ion-exchange isotherms. The enthalpies of reaction and the corresponding entropy values were calculated. The thermodynamic functions for different cations depend upon the hydrated radii of ingoing cation.

A number of studies of the temperature dependence of ion exchange reaction on synthetic organic resins have been reported^{1,2,3,4}. Inorganic ion exchangers are also being developed with great interest and their respective studies are in order. Zirconium phosphate has been studied in greater detail⁵ as a synthetic inorganic ion exchanger. Larsen⁶ studied the equilibria of $Li^+ - H^+$, $Na^+ - H^+$ and $K^+ - H^+$ on zirconium phosphate. Baetsle⁷ studied the tracer ion equilibria on zirconyl phosphate in hydrogen form with Rb^+ , Cs^+ , Sr^{2+} , Ce^{3+} and Eu^{3+} . Nancollas⁸ determined the equilibrium exchange of Li^+ , K^+ and Cs^+ ions with the hydrogen form of semicrystalline zirconium phosphate at a constant ionic strength. Recently, thermodynamics of exchange of hydrated transition metal ions in ammonium mordenite was studied by Barrer⁹. The ion exchange characteristics of tantalum arsenate are of considerable interest because of the possible use of this material as a cation exchanger and its application for the separation of rare earth ions¹⁰. Kinetic studies on the exchange of Ag^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Y^{3+} and Th^{4+} ions with hydrogen ion on tantalum arsenate have been reported¹¹. The ion exchange was found to be particle diffusion controlled and depend upon the hydrated radii of the ingoing cations.

The present report concerns the influence of temperature on the equilibria of $Mg^{2+} - H^+$, $Ca^{2+} - H^+$, $Sr^{2+} - H^+$, $Ba^{2+} - H^+$, $La^{3+} - H^+$ and $Th^{4+} - H^+$ with respect to tantalum arsenate at constant ionic strength within the temperature range from 20 to 50°.

Experimental

Reagents : Tantalum pentoxide (BARC, India) and sodium arsenate (Riedel, Germany) were used. All other reagents used were of AnalaR grade.

22.10 g of tantalum pentoxide was heated with 200 g of ammonium sulphate in 200 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid. The clear solution was diluted to 500 ml to obtain a solution which was 0.1N with respect to tantalum. Sodium arsenate (0.1N) solution was prepared in 2N hydrochloric acid.

Tantalum arsenate, synthesized as reported in our earlier work^{10,11} was sieved to 50-100 mesh and washed free from fine particles. The hydrogen form of the exchanger was prepared with 2N nitric acid and was converted to the respective metal ion forms by placing the exchanger in 0.1N solutions of the metal chlorides or nitrates for 24 hrs with intermittent replacement of the solution. All samples were washed free of chloride ions, air dried and equilibrated to constant weight in an atmosphere of 51% humidity.

The water contents of the various samples of the exchanger was determined by heating to constant weight in an air oven at 200°. The exchange capacities were found by eluting with 2N hydrochloric acid in a column and analysing the effluent for alkaline earth metal ions, with EDTA, using Eriochrome black T as indicator, and lanthanum and thorium, using xylenol orange as indicator.

Equilibration experiments : In the equilibration experiments, 0.2 g samples of the hydrogen form of the exchanger were shaken at the desired temperature in an electric SICO shaker for 6 hrs with 20 ml of a solution containing hydrochloric acid or nitric acid, the appropriate alkaline earth metal chloride, and lanthanum and thorium nitrates at a total ionic strength of 0.1N. Experiment showed that equilibrium was attained within this period and the supernatant solution was analysed for the metal ions. The experiments were conducted at 20, 30, 40 and 50° with $\pm 1^\circ$ variation.

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Reversibility test : Before equilibrium thermodynamic procedures could be applied to any experimental isotherm data, it was necessary to establish that true equilibrium conditions existed over the whole isotherm. Thus isotherm points were measured in the reverse direction also, starting with the metal exchanged form of the tantalum arsenate. The term "reversible" as used in this paper means that true equilibrium conditions were found to exist over the whole isotherm, that is, the forward and reverse isotherms coincided within experimental uncertainty.

Reversibility test was made by the conventional method of equilibrating known weights of tantalum arsenate maximally exchanged by the magnesium ion with isotherm solution in the manner described in the previous section.

Results and Discussion

Capacity and water content measurements : The ion exchange capacity and water content values for magnesium, calcium, strontium, barium, lanthanum and thorium forms of the exchanger are given in Table 1. It can be seen that the capacity for the

TABLE 1—WATER CONTENT AND ION EXCHANGE CAPACITY OF SOME METAL IONS ON TANTALUM ARSENATE

Metal ion	Water Content (%)	Ion Exchange Capacity of Cationic form of Exchanger (meq/g)	Ion Exchange Capacity of Hydrogen form of Exchanger (meq/g)
Mg ²⁺	17.20	0.82	0.98
Ca ²⁺	14.47	0.88	1.09
Sr ²⁺	10.18	0.92	1.14
Ba ²⁺	10.13	0.97	1.21
La ³⁺	10.36	0.68	0.92
Th ⁴⁺	11.18	0.52	0.78

alkaline earth metal chloride solution increases in the order Mg²⁺ < Ca²⁺ < Sr²⁺ < Ba²⁺. Similar variations of the capacity of zirconium phosphate with the nature of the ingoing cation have been observed by other workers^{12,13}. The values of ion exchange capacity and water content indicate that the metals enter the matrix as hydrated ions and the marked difference in the capacity can be accounted for the differences in the number of associated water dipoles. Sites close to the hydrated metal ions may thus be effectively blocked for the exchange reaction. In addition to the above factors it is well known that tantalum arsenate exhibits ion-sieve properties resulting in an uptake which would be governed by the relative sizes of the hydrated alkaline earth ions in agreement with the observed order of capacities. Analogous behaviour was found by other workers¹⁴ on zirconium phosphate.

Ion-exchange isotherms : The study of different cations and reversibility test for the exchange

reaction Mg²⁺-H⁺ indicate that the exchange is reversible under the experimental error range. The selectivity coefficient for the reaction

is defined by

$$S = \frac{\bar{X}_M (X_H)^n}{X_M (\bar{X}_H)^n} \quad \dots (2)$$

where \bar{X}_M and \bar{X}_H refer to the equivalent fractions of the metal and hydrogen ions in the exchanger and X_M and X_H , the equivalent fraction of the metal and hydrogen ions in the solution.

The thermodynamic equilibrium constant for the reaction (1) may be written in terms of activity coefficients, f ,

$$K_H^M = \frac{\bar{X}_M \cdot f_M (X_H)^n \cdot (f_H)^n}{X_M \cdot f_M (\bar{X}_H)^n \cdot (f_H)^n} = S \cdot \frac{\bar{f}_M (f_H)^n}{f_M (\bar{f}_H)^n} \quad \dots (3)$$

The ratio of activity coefficients in the solution, f_H/f_M can be calculated from the mean ionic activity coefficients of pure salt solutions at same ionic strength of 0.1N by the method due to Glueckauf¹⁵, since these dilute solutions will not deviate greatly from ionic strength principle at 20° to 50°, neglect of the temperature dependence of the activity coefficients ratio will not be serious deviation in the values of K_H^M especially for ion exchange reactions^{8,16,17}, therefore the thermodynamic equilibrium constant is obtained as

$$K_H^M = S \cdot \frac{\bar{f}_M}{(f_H)^n} \quad \dots (4)$$

The solid phase activity coefficients are given by¹⁸

$$\ln \bar{f}_M = -(1 - \bar{X}_M) \ln S + \int_{\bar{X}_M}^1 \ln S \, d\bar{X}_M \quad \dots (5)$$

and

$$\ln \bar{f}_H = \bar{X}_M \ln S \int_0^{\bar{X}_M} \ln S \, d\bar{X}_M \quad \dots (6)$$

By numerical integration of log S against \bar{X}_M curves using the above relationships, the solid phase activity coefficients and the thermodynamic equilibrium constants given in Tables 2 and 3 were calculated for the exchange of hydrogen ion with Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba, La and Th ions.

TABLE 2—SELECTIVITY COEFFICIENTS AND SOLID PHASE ACTIVITY COEFFICIENTS FOR Mg^{2+} -H EXCHANGE AT $20 \pm 1^\circ C$

X_{Mg}	\bar{X}_{Mg}	S_H^{Mg}	\bar{f}_{Mg}	\bar{f}_H	K_H^{Mg}
0.025	0.022	0.8919	0.44	1.02	0.377
0.050	0.038	0.7444	0.52	1.01	0.379
0.102	0.062	0.5610	0.67	0.99	0.378
0.150	0.084	0.4831	0.78	0.97	0.388
0.212	0.121	0.4616	0.79	0.96	0.395
0.253	0.144	0.4345	0.81	0.94	0.398
0.325	0.214	0.4849	0.79	0.97	0.389
0.389	0.267	0.4888	0.78	0.98	0.397
0.454	0.288	0.3716	0.85	0.90	0.389
0.537	0.302	0.2479	0.90	0.75	0.396
0.612	0.322	0.1714	0.95	0.64	0.397
0.755	0.348	0.0652	1.21	0.44	0.407

 Mean $K = 0.391$

 TABLE 3—MEAN THERMODYNAMIC EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANT (K_H^M) VALUES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Exchange	K_H^M (mean)	Exchange	K_H^M (mean)
$Mg^{2+}-H^+$	0.391	$Mg^{2+}-H^+$	0.453
$Ca^{2+}-H^+$	0.471	$Ca^{2+}-H^+$	0.695
$Sr^{2+}-H^+$	0.557	$Sr^{2+}-H^+$	0.625
$Ba^{2+}-H^+$	0.893	$Ba^{2+}-H^+$	1.070
$La^{3+}-H^+$	0.553	$La^{3+}-H^+$	0.692
$Th^{4+}-H^+$	0.159	$Th^{4+}-H^+$	0.215
Exchange	K_H^M (mean)	Exchange	K_H^M (mean)
$Mg^{2+}-H^+$	0.555	$Mg^{2+}-H^+$	0.623
$Ca^{2+}-H^+$	0.835	$Ca^{2+}-H^+$	0.950
$Sr^{2+}-H^+$	0.732	$Sr^{2+}-H^+$	0.787
$Ba^{2+}-H^+$	1.353	$Ba^{2+}-H^+$	1.537
$La^{3+}-H^+$	0.892	$La^{3+}-H^+$	1.102
$Th^{4+}-H^+$	0.311	$Th^{4+}-H^+$	0.433

The free energy changes, $\Delta G'$ for the ion exchange were calculated from the thermodynamic equilibrium constants using the general relation

$$\Delta G' = - \frac{RT}{Z_H \cdot Z_M} \ln K_H^M \quad \dots (7)$$

where R is the gas constant, Z_H , Z_M are the valence of competing ionic species, T is the absolute temperature. The free energy changes, $\Delta G'$ are given in Table 4.

 TABLE 4—THERMODYNAMIC PROPERTIES FOR THE EXCHANGE OF METAL IONS WITH HYDROGEN ION ON TANTALUM ARSENATE AT $20 \pm 1^\circ C$

Displacing Ion	ΔG° (Cal mole $^{-1}$)	ΔH° (Cal mole $^{-1}$)	ΔS° (Cal deg $^{-1}$ mole $^{-1}$)	ΔS_{EX} (Cal deg $^{-1}$ mole $^{-1}$)
Mg^{2+}	276	-1241	-5.1	-36.7
Ca^{2+}	220	-1454	-5.7	-17.1
Sr^{2+}	171	-1105	-4.3	-11.6
Ba^{2+}	93	-1666	-5.8	-3.5
La^{3+}	116	-1579	-5.8	-49.8
Th^{4+}	270	-2727	-10.2	—

The ΔH° values are calculated from the plot of $\log_{10} K$ against $1/T$. The ΔH° values for the exchange of the alkaline earth metals and hydrogen ion show that heat was evolved. In general ΔH° appeared to be a function of the difference of the hydration of the exchanging cations and was small for ions of similar hydration number and large for ions of widely differing hydration number.

The entropy changes, ΔS° corresponding to the ion exchange process were calculated using the equation

$$\Delta S^\circ = \frac{\Delta H^\circ - \Delta G^\circ}{T} \quad \dots (8)$$

The calculated ΔS° values are given in Table 4. The entropy differences between the corresponding ionic forms of the exchanger, ΔS_{EX} can be written^{1,2}

$$\Delta S^\circ = \Delta S_{EX} - (S_M^\circ - S_H^\circ) \quad \dots (9)$$

where S° = the aqueous ionic entropies²⁰. Values of ΔS_{EX} are included in Table 4 and reflect (i) changes in hydration accompanying reaction (1) and (ii) the differences in lattice distortion of the two forms of the exchanger. The ΔS_{EX} values in Table 4 show a significant increase with the size of the ingoing cation. The observed order $Mg < Ca < Sr < Ba$ is consistent with the proposed increasing hydration of the alkaline earth metal ions within the exchanger. It is seen that this trend becomes apparent only after removing the variable ($S_M^\circ - S_H^\circ$) term from the measured ΔS° . The change in entropy, ΔS° shows no correlation with the hydrated ionic radius but increases slightly in magnitude as a linear functions of the bare ion radius. On this basis, the exchange is envisaged as occurring between the covalently bound hydrogen and hydrated cations in the interstitial liquid, the affinity being inversely proportional to the degree of hydration during exchange the polarized hydration shell is displaced and the liberated hydrogen ion become hydrated. The net change in entropy equals that due to the replacement of one cation by another plus the entropy difference between the hydrated forms of the two ions involved, and the overall value of ΔS° is thus less for very large hydrated ions. Sr^{2+} ion does not follow the general trend probably due to the hydrolysis of the Sr^{2+} in neutral solutions ($Sr^{2+} + H_2O \rightarrow SrOH^+ + H^+$).

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